

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

MARKETING STRATEGIES AS A TOOL FOR MANAGING ENTERPRISE COMPETITIVENESS

Rakviashvili A.

Doctor of Business Administration (Ph. D.)

Visiting Lecturer at G. Robakidze University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20186427>

Abstract

The relevance of the topic is reflected in the fact that, according to the State Statistics Service, 758,478 enterprises were registered in Georgia in 2020, representing a 5% increase from the same period last year. The quantitative growth of companies creates competition, new markets, and forces commercial organizations to use new tools to maintain and increase sales volumes. This means that marketing in Georgian companies is moving to a new level of development. Innovations should primarily concern small and medium-sized enterprises, since they are relatively more flexible in the face of change. Marketing in such companies, as they say, is more “plastic” and allows testing various strategies for both product promotion and the company’s marketing structure. Thus, the chosen topic is relevant because of the need to develop marketing in Georgian enterprises.

Purpose and objectives of the work. The purpose of the work is to develop a marketing strategy for the company. To achieve this, it was necessary to solve the following logically interconnected tasks: (i) study the concept and specifics of marketing in the industrial sphere, the specifics of competitiveness, (ii) determination of methods for assessing competitiveness and comparison of their effectiveness; (iii) definition of the content of marketing strategy as a tool for managing competitiveness.

Subject and object of research. The object of research is marketing strategies. The subject of research is the marketing activities of the company “Elite Motors”.

The practical significance of the work lies in the potential to use the developed system to promote goods and services within a Georgian company. This strategy has been tested in the Georgian company “Elite Motors”.

Keywords: enterprise marketing strategies, marketing strategy models, functional strategies.

1. Introduction

A market economy implies the existence of competition. Today, there are several definitions of competition in the economic literature:

a) “the existence of a large number of independently acting buyers and sellers of any specific product or resource in the market”;

b) “a situation when buyers and sellers freely enter or leave markets”.

c) In the Law of Georgia “On Competition”, adopted on May 8, 2012, competition is defined as “rivalry between economic agents operating or potentially operating in the relevant market for gaining an advantage in this market”.

The law defines the organizational and legal basis for deterring, restricting, and preventing monopolistic activities and unfair competition. It aims to ensure the conditions for the creation and effective functioning of commodity markets. It does not apply to relations governed by the norms of the legal protection of inventions, trademarks, and copyrights, except in cases provided by law.

2. Variety of marketing strategies and models of their use in the company “Elite Motors.”

The basis of each marketing strategy of the company “Elite Motors” is an executive plan, by which the company achieves its set goals. Of the two theoretically known main marketing goals, at different times (depending on the strategic goals), it contains one of the following:

1. A plan for attracting clients (buyers);
2. A plan for promoting the product.

In any marketing strategy of the company “Elite Motors”, a competent analysis of the market and the sphere in which the company plans to operate is very important. Such niches may differ in size, scope, target audience, and potential profitability. In most cases, each such niche requires an individual approach from the marketing strategist.

In addition, the following factors should be taken into account: product features, target audience, market opportunities, promotion methods, distribution, and sales.

Thus, the marketing strategy of the company “Elite Motors” corresponds to the following goals:

- Assessment of real solvent demand for the product and methods of its distribution;
- Assessment of market capacity, according to which distribution will be carried out;
- Analysis of risks that may arise during product promotion and marketing;
- Analysis of real and potential products of competitors;
- Assessment of the sustainability and efficiency of product production and distribution.

The main types of marketing strategies for “Elite Motors” are: global, basic, growth, competitive, new, and functional, which we will discuss in the next chapter.

3. Results of activities carried out in 2021-2022 within the framework of the study at the company “Elite Motors.”

In 2021-2022, as in 2020, when the pandemic began, the company “Elite Motors” continued its development and even experienced significant growth.

Of course, this was also due to the company's marketing department. But it should be noted that within the framework of the study, the company's management

decided to try a new type of marketing strategy for itself- functional. Functional strategies are presented in Table 1.

Table 1.

Types of functional marketing strategies

Functional strategy name	Functional strategy name
Assortment strategy	Assortment strategy
Development strategy	Development strategy
Distribution strategy	Distribution strategy
Pricing strategy	Pricing strategy
Target market selection strategy	Target market selection strategy

When summarizing the activities and results of 2021, it turned out that the implementation of the new functional strategy gave us the following picture: The company "Elite Motors" conducted lead campaigns:

- Diesel generators,
- Nitrogen generators,
- Air compressors,
- Mekalaco-excavator loader

A lead is, first of all, the client's interest in the company and the contact established with it.

In the strict sense, a lead is a potential customer who responds to marketing communications in a way that enables the seller to understand his needs and capabilities and assess his sales potential. In this sense, a lead is not only the contacts left by a potential buyer and/or another person, but also a specific combination of the client's interests and desires, as well as the seller's belief in the prospects for further communication.

Depending on the scope and goals of the marketing campaign, the understanding of a lead's characteristics and the amount of information it contains may change. For example, market penetration can be done in several steps. It can collect different amounts of customer data (including the customer's position in the company) if we are talking about b2b marketing.

In general, any client contact information can be considered a lead, but questions arise regarding the type and qualification of the lead.

In addition, an advertising video was placed at Gldani Mall as an outdoor campaign.

Let's consider the impressive results we achieved:

- Diesel generators - 124 leads,
- Nitrogen generators - 35 leads,
- Air compressors - 117 leads,
- Mekalaco-excavator loader - 17 leads.

In exchange for the \$345 spent on the lead campaign, the company reached up to 150,000 business clients (Geostat's business database, filtered by areas of activity). The advertisement placed as a result of the outdoor campaign was seen by 360 thousand people.

Among the innovations planned for 2022, it is worth noting:

- 2 professionally edited posts per month on all pages;
- One professionally written blog per month on news;
- One blog per month about products and their features, which will highlight the positive aspects and advantages.

As for general marketing activities, the following were planned within the framework of the study:

- a) Renewing visits to BMG by starting to discuss large projects of partners;
- b) Special offer for the business club;
- c) In the best case, shooting and editing 2 videos per year about the company's path and growth prospects;
- d) Create a Wikipedia page for the company "Elite Motors" (in the coming months);
- e) In addition to TV Pirveli, on which the company's activities are systematically covered within the framework of the research (3 programs), start cooperation with several other online media;
- f) Register the company "Elite Motors" in Google My Business and create an account.

Marketing activities planned and implemented in 2022 are presented in Table 2.

In addition, the company, not within the framework of research, but based on its own business goals, conducts marketing activities for FB/INSTA, namely:

- Photo projects at locations using the equipment of "Elite Motors",
- A column of small video discussions, led by a specialist in each direction (one video per month);
- Posting blogs;
- Posting informational posts on each brand of Elite Motors;
- Live broadcasts and Q&A on Instagram, raffles.

Period	Activity
January-February	• SEO optimization (in terms of content and backend);
February	• Starting work on the creation of news;
March	• Ordering a blog.
Until the end of the year	• Visiting BMJ;
Until the end of the year	• Taking photos with partners;
Until the end of the year	• Recording a video review.
Until the end of the year	The path of "Elite Motors."

Conclusion

The strategy for promoting goods and services today is a key element of the research company's marketing plan; it sets out the goals of advertising campaigns, basic approaches to marketing communications, and tools for promoting products in the market.

1. To build a motivation system, it is necessary to introduce non-financial indicators of employee performance;

2. The salary of sales managers should depend on their professional knowledge and skills, planned and already concluded contracts, the level of customer satisfaction, etc. In addition, a system of additional bonus payments is needed, which is tied to the total value of the contract concluded by the employee, or to the importance of the client for the organization;

3. An annual bonus can be used as an effective motivation tool, the calculation of which will be based on the analysis of indicators obtained as a result of monitoring the level of customer satisfaction. For a sales manager, an annual bonus is an additional incentive to stay in the organization;

4. To manage the current situation, the head of the sales department should flexibly and promptly change the motivation goals so that they are fully consistent with the organization's ongoing goals. The change process should begin with providing employees with full information about the planned changes. The information should include: the reasons for the changes, their scope, implementation deadlines, and a list of benefits that the change will bring to employees. Employees should be well informed about all changes, since the approaches to managers in this area are special and in this market segment, even positive experience from other industries cannot be thoughtlessly used;

5. Salary alone is not enough to motivate a sales manager. Here, a direct connection between the efforts made, the results achieved, and the amount of compensation "works" much better. That is why it is important to show them the principle by which the remuneration is calculated;

6. In the process of developing an incentive system, it is necessary to take into account the level and structure of the incentive package offered by competitors under similar conditions. That is, to create an effective incentive system that drives sales growth and improves quality, it is not enough to rely solely on standard schemes. A creative approach, a deep understanding of the organization's business processes, and consideration of sales managers' personal, professional, and psychological characteristics are required.

References:

1. 4 Key Ingredients To An Effective B2B Promotions Strategy/Blog. Limehub, 2020. URL: <https://www.limehub.com.au/blog/4-key-ingredients-to-an-effective-b2b-promotions-strategy>
2. Abbamonte K. How to Develop a B2B Marketing Strategy (Instead of a List of Tactics) [Electronic resource] / Blog. Leadfeeder.com, 2020. URL: [https://hingemarketing.com/blog/story/10-essential-b2b-marketing-strategies-to-grow-your-](https://hingemarketing.com/blog/story/10-essential-b2b-marketing-strategies-to-grow-your-professional-services-firm)

[professional-services-firm](https://www.leadfeeder.com/blog/develop-a-b2b-marketing-strategy/) (дата обращения: 29.05.2020).

3. Abbamonte K. How to Develop a B2B Marketing Strategy (Instead of a List of Tactics)/ Blog. Leadfeeder.com, 2020.

4. Atkinson J.H., et al (2019). Current Trends in Cost of Quality (Montvale, NJ, National Association of Accountants Publication № 91259.

5. Chen J. Contextual Advertising /Publications. Investopedia.com, 2019.

6. Chen J. Contextual Advertising/Publications. Investopedia.com, 2019. URL: <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/c/contextualadvertising.asp>

7. Chrisos M. The Benefits of Contextual Marketing for B2B/Publications. Techfunnel.com, 2018. URL: <https://www.techfunnel.com/martech/the-benefits-of-contextual-marketing-for-b2b/>

8. Competitive Strategy: Techniques for Analyzing Industries and Competitors. — New York: The Free Press, 1980 (2nd ed. — New York: Free Press, 1998. — 397 p

9. Crafts Nicholas. Globalization and Growth in the Twentieth Century, IMF Working Paper, WP-00-04, IMF, 2012

10. Dan Vasile. Industrial and competitive strategies and structures, All Educational Publishing House. Bucharest, 1997

11. Doug J. Chung "How to Really Motivate Salespeople", april 2015; <https://hbr.org/2015/04/how-to-really-motivate-salespeople>

12. Dunning J. Multinational Enterprises and the Global Economy, Addison–Wesley, 2014

13. Durant J. Maximize ROI: How to Promote Your B2B Website/Blog. Bopdesign.com, 2017. URL: <https://www.bopdesign.com/bop-blog/2017/01/maximize-roi-promote-b2b-website/>

14. Frederiksen L. B2B Website Strategy: The Expertise Driven Sale/ Blog. Hingemarketing.com, 2018.

15. Harr E. 11 Strategies for B2B Website Development [Electronic resource] / Blog. B2bnn.com, 2018. URL: <https://www.b2bnn.com/2018/04/11-strategies-b2b-website-development/>

16. Held David, McGrew Anthony, Goldblatt David and Perraton Jonathan. Global changes: politics, economy and culture, Polirom Publishing House, Iași, 2001

17. Hill Charles. International Business: Competing in the Global Marketplace, McGraw-Hill Companies; 2-nd edition, 1998.

18. Hugues Kirsty, European Competitiveness, Cambridge University Press, pg. 5, 1998.

19. Joe Pulizzi, Content Inc.: How Entrepreneurs Use Content to Build Massive Audiences and Create Radically Successful Businesses; September 8, 2015

20. Kammerer M. The Value of Contextual Advertising on Today's Internet/ Publications.Buysellads.com, 2019. URL: <https://content.buysellads.com/articles/the-value-of-context-on-todays-internet>

21. New features & announcements/Google Ads Help, 2020. URL: <https://support.google.com/google-ads/announcements/9048695>

22. Patel S. The Top 11 Most Effective B2B Marketing Strategies for 2020/Blog. Sujanpatel.com, 2020. URL: <https://sujanpatel.com/marketing/b2b-strategy/113>
23. Patel S. The Top 11 Most Effective B2B Marketing Strategies for 2020
24. Porter Michael, From competitive advantage to corporate strategy, Harvard Business Review, no 3,1987
25. Promotional Strategy: Sound Your Horn / Publications. B2Binternational.com, 2020.
26. Promotional Strategy: Sound Your Horn/Publications. B2Binternational.com, 2020. URL: <https://www.b2binternational.com/publications/promotional-strategy-sound-horn/>
27. Rajagopal. (2007) Marketing Dynamics: Theory and Practice. New Delhi, India: New Age International. Retrieved April 5, 2010
28. Reichheld, Frederick F. (December 2003). "One Number You Need to Grow". Harvard Business Review.
29. Salmi J. (2000). Facing the Challenges of the Twenty-First Century // Intern. Higher Education (USA).№ 19. P. 2–3.
30. Selling to Other Businesses: 8 Sales Promotion Methods for a B2B Market [Electronic resource]/Publications. Business.com, 2020. URL:
31. Selling to Other Businesses: 8 Sales Promotion Methods for a B2B Market/ Publications. Business.com, 2020.
32. Specific interrelations of Politics and Economics in Russian History. Political Events and Economic Ideas (Ed. By I. Bahrens, V.Caspari, B. Schefold). Edward Elgar, 2004
33. Vrountas T. Contextual Advertising 101: How it Works, Benefits & Why It's Necessary for Relevant Ads/Publications. Instapage.com, 2020. URL: <https://instapage.com/blog/contextual-advertising>
34. Vrountas T. Contextual Advertising 101: How it Works, Benefits & Why It's Necessary for Relevant Ads/Publications. Instapage.com,2020.